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Derivation of the Uncertainty Equations

The water vapour amount fraction, x_w , at the generator gas outlet is given by the equation:

$$x_w = \frac{f(T_{\text{sat}}, p) \cdot e_w(T_{\text{sat}})}{p} \quad (1)$$

where $e_w(T_{\text{sat}})$ is the saturation vapour pressure over ice at the temperature T_{sat} , p is the total system pressure and $f(T_{\text{sat}}, p)$ is the water vapour enhancement factor, which takes into account the non-ideal behaviour of the gas mixture.

The combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w)$, is thus given by:

$$u_c(x_w) = \sqrt{\left[x_w \left(\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} + \frac{1}{e_w} \frac{\partial e_w}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} \right) \right]^2 \cdot u_c^2(T_{\text{sat}}) + \left[x_w \left(\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial p} - \frac{1}{p} \right) \right]^2 \cdot u_c^2(p) + \left(\frac{e_w}{p} \right)^2 \cdot u^2(f) + \left(\frac{f}{p} \right)^2 \cdot u^2(e_w)} \quad (2)$$

where

$u_c(T_{\text{sat}})$ and $u_c(p)$ are the combined measurement uncertainties of the saturation temperature and the pressure, respectively;

$u(e_w)$ and $u(f)$ are the standard uncertainties of $e_w(T_{\text{sat}})$ and $f(T_{\text{sat}}, p)$, respectively;

the terms

$$x_w \left(\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} + \frac{1}{e_w} \frac{\partial e_w}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} \right), \quad x_w \left(\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial p} - \frac{1}{p} \right), \quad \frac{e_w}{p} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{f}{p}$$
 are the relevant sensitivity coefficients.

Equation 2 is determined applying the general law of uncertainty propagation to the equation 1, which can be rewritten as follows:

$$x_w = \frac{f(T_{\text{sat}}, p, \omega) \cdot e_w(T_{\text{sat}}, \lambda)}{p} \quad (3)$$

where the quantities ω and λ are introduced to take into account the uncertainties associated with the equations used to formulate the enhancement factor and the saturation vapour pressure over ice respectively [1]. The quantities ω and λ are considered as multipliers with an estimated value of 1 and an uncertainty equal to the relative uncertainty of the calculated values.

Thus $\lambda = 1$ and $u(\lambda) = u_r(e_w)$, and $\omega = 1$ and $u(\omega) = u_r(f)$, where $u_r(e_w)$ is estimated by using the formulation given by the 2011 IAPWS release for the sublimation pressure of ice *Ih* [2], while the estimation of $u_r(f)$ is based on the work of Lovell-Smith [3].

The total uncertainty of x_w is then determined considering the partial derivatives with respect to the relevant quantities T_{sat} , p , ω and λ , reported below:

$$\frac{\partial x_w}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} = \frac{\partial x_w}{\partial f} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} + \frac{\partial x_w}{\partial e_w} \cdot \frac{\partial e_w}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} = \frac{e_w}{p} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} + \frac{f}{p} \cdot \frac{\partial e_w}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} = \frac{f \cdot e_w}{p} \left(\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} + \frac{1}{e_w} \frac{\partial e_w}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} \right) = x_w \left(\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} + \frac{1}{e_w} \frac{\partial e_w}{\partial T_{\text{sat}}} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial x_w}{\partial p} = \frac{\partial x_w}{\partial f} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial p} - \frac{1}{p^2} \cdot f \cdot e_w = \frac{e_w}{p} \frac{\partial f}{\partial p} - \frac{1}{p^2} \cdot f \cdot e_w = \frac{f \cdot e_w}{p} \left(\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial p} - \frac{1}{p} \right) = x_w \left(\frac{1}{f} \frac{\partial f}{\partial p} - \frac{1}{p} \right) \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\partial x_w}{\partial \omega} = \frac{\partial x_w}{\partial f} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \omega} = \frac{e_w}{p} f \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial x_w}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{\partial x_w}{\partial e_w} \cdot \frac{\partial e_w}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{f}{p} e_w \quad (7)$$

Estimation of the measurement uncertainty

The detailed uncertainty contributions considered for the estimation of the measurement uncertainty of T_{fp} , p and x_w in the whole working range of interest are reported in the following tables.

Table 1: INRIM 03 uncertainty budget for the frost-point temperature, T_{fp} , pressure, p , and water vapour amount fraction, x_w at the following nominal values: $T_{\text{fp}} = -75$ °C, $p = 1100$ hPa and $x_w = 1118$ nmol·mol⁻¹.

$T_{\text{fp}} = -75$ °C $p = 1100$ hPa $x_w = 1118$ nmol·mol⁻¹				
Uncertainty budget for T_{fp} / °C				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/°C
Saturation temperature repeatability	0.00088 °C	Normal	1	8.8·10 ⁻⁴
Saturator temperature uniformity	0.000086 °C	Rectangular	1	8.6·10 ⁻⁴
SPRT calibration	0.00025 °C	Normal	1	2.5·10 ⁻⁴
Temperature resistance bridge accuracy	0.00043 °C	Rectangular	1	4.3·10 ⁻⁴
SPRT drift	0.0017 °C	Rectangular	1	1.7·10 ⁻³
Self-heating SPRT	0.00066 °C	Asym. Triangular	1	1.6·10 ⁻⁴
Adsorption/Desorption	0.034 °C	Normal	1	3.4·10 ⁻²
Saturation efficiency	0.0068 °C	Rectangular	1	6.8·10 ⁻³
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(T_{\text{fp}})$ / °C				0.034
Uncertainty budget for p /Pa				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/Pa
Pressure control stability	5.4 Pa	U-distribution	1	5.4

Transducer calibration	3.3 Pa	Normal	1	3.3
Long term stability	15.1 Pa	Rectangular	1	15.1
Linearity and temperature effects	7.6 Pa	Rectangular	1	7.6
Resolution	0.03 Pa	Rectangular	1	0.03
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(p)$ / Pa				18.0
Uncertainty budget for x_w / mol·mol⁻¹				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty / mol·mol ⁻¹
Saturation pure water vapour pressure, $e(T_{fp})$	0.0002 Pa	Normal	$9.18 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$2.15 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Enhancement factor, $f(T_{fp}, p)$	0.0005	Normal	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.65 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Frost point temperature, T_{fp}	0.034 °C	Normal	$1.80 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ °C}^{-1}$	$6.19 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Pressure, p	18.0 Pa	Normal	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$3.09 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w)$ / mol·mol⁻¹				$6.58 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Percent relative standard uncertainty, $100 \cdot u_c(x_w) / x_w$				0.59

Table 2: INRIM 03 uncertainty budget for the frost-point temperature, T_{fp} , pressure, p , and water vapour amount fraction, x_w at the following nominal values: $T_{fp} = -75 \text{ °C}$, $p = 200 \text{ hPa}$ and $x_w = 6104 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$.

$T_{fp} = -75 \text{ °C}$ $p = 200 \text{ hPa}$ $x_w = 6104 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$				
Uncertainty budget for T_{fp} / °C				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty / °C
Saturation temperature repeatability	0.00077 °C	Normal	1	$7.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Saturator temperature uniformity	0.00028 °C	Rectangular	1	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT calibration	0.00025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Temperature resistance bridge accuracy	0.00043 °C	Rectangular	1	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT drift	0.0017 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Self-heating SPRT	0.00066 °C	Asym. Triangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Adsorption/Desorption	0.032 °C	Normal	1	$3.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Saturation efficiency	0.00082 °C	Rectangular	1	$8.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(T_{fp})$ / °C				0.032
Uncertainty budget for p / Pa				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty / Pa
Pressure control stability	3.7 Pa	U-distribution	1	3.7
Transducer calibration	2.0 Pa	Normal	1	2.0
Long term stability	15.1 Pa	Rectangular	1	15.1

Linearity and temperature effects	7.6 Pa	Rectangular	1	7.6
Resolution	0.03 Pa	Rectangular	1	0.03
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(p)$ /Pa				17.4
Uncertainty budget for x_w /mol·mol⁻¹				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ mol·mol ⁻¹
Saturation pure water vapour pressure, $e(T_{fp})$	0.00024 Pa	Normal	$5.01 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$1.18 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Enhancement factor, $f(T_{fp}, p)$	0.000087	Normal	$6.21 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5.39 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Frost point temperature, T_{fp}	0.032 °C	Normal	$9.74 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ °C}^{-1}$	$3.12 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Pressure, p	17.4 Pa	Normal	$2.64 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$4.59 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w)$ / mol·mol⁻¹				$3.37 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Percent relative standard uncertainty, $100 \cdot u_c(x_w) / x_w$				0.55

Table 3: INRIM 03 uncertainty budget on the frost-point temperature, T_{fp} , pressure, p , and water vapour amount fraction, x_w at the following nominal values $T_{fp} = -90$ °C, $p = 1100$ hPa and $x_w = 89$ nmol·mol⁻¹.

$T_{fp} = -90$ °C $p = 1100$ hPa $x_w = 89$ nmol·mol⁻¹				
Uncertainty budget for T_{fp} / °C				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty / °C
Saturation temperature repeatability	0.00079 °C	Normal	1	$7.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Saturator temperature uniformity	0.00059 °C	Rectangular	1	$5.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT calibration	0.00025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Temperature resistance bridge accuracy	0.00043 °C	Rectangular	1	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT drift	0.0017 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Self-heating SPRT	0.00066 °C	Asym. Triangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Adsorption/Desorption	0.027 °C	Normal	1	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Saturation efficiency	0.012 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(T_{fp})$ / °C				0.030
Uncertainty budget for p /Pa				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ Pa
Pressure control stability	6.8 Pa	U-distribution	1	6.8
Transducer calibration	3.1 Pa	Normal	1	3.1
Long term stability	15.1 Pa	Rectangular	1	15.1
Linearity and temperature effects	7.6 Pa	Rectangular	1	7.6
Resolution	0.03 Pa	Rectangular	1	0.03

Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(p)$ / Pa				18.5
Uncertainty budget for x_w / mol·mol⁻¹				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ mol·mol ⁻¹
Saturation pure water vapour pressure, $e(T_{fp})$	0.000023 Pa	Normal	$9.18 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$2.09 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Enhancement factor, $f(T_{fp}, p)$	0.00063	Normal	$8.39 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$5.24 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Frost point temperature, T_{fp}	0.030 °C	Normal	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ °C}^{-1}$	$4.69 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Pressure, p	18.5 Pa	Normal	$1.41 \cdot 10^{-14} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$2.61 \cdot 10^{-13}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w)$ / mol·mol⁻¹				$5.17 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Percent relative standard uncertainty, $100 \cdot u_c(x_w) / x_w$				0.58

Table 4: INRIM 03 uncertainty budget on the frost-point temperature, T_{fp} , pressure, p , and water vapour amount fraction, x_w at the following nominal values $T_{fp} = -90$ °C, $p = 200$ hPa and $x_w = 484$ nmol·mol⁻¹.

$T_{fp} = -90$ °C $p = 200$ hPa $x_w = 484$ nmol·mol⁻¹				
Uncertainty budget for T_{fp} / °C				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ °C
Saturation temperature repeatability	0.0017 °C	Normal	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Saturator temperature uniformity	0.00014 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT calibration	0.00025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Temperature resistance bridge accuracy	0.00043 °C	Rectangular	1	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT drift	0.0017 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Self-heating SPRT	0.00066 °C	Asym. Triangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Adsorption/Desorption	0.027 °C	Normal	1	$2.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Saturation efficiency	0.0016 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(T_{fp})$ / °C				0.027
Uncertainty budget for p / Pa				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ Pa
Pressure control stability	4.1 Pa	U-distribution	1	4.1
Transducer calibration	2.0 Pa	Normal	1	2.0
Long term stability	15.1 Pa	Rectangular	1	15.1
Linearity and temperature effects	7.6 Pa	Rectangular	1	7.6
Resolution	0.03 Pa	Rectangular	1	0.03
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(p)$ / Pa				17.5

Uncertainty budget for x_w / mol·mol⁻¹				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	Probability distribution	Sensitivity Coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ mol·mol ⁻¹
Saturation pure water vapour pressure, $e(T_{fp})$	0.000023 Pa	Normal	$5.01 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Enhancement factor, $f(T_{fp}, p)$	0.00011	Normal	$4.62 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$5.17 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Frost point temperature, T_{fp}	0.027 °C	Normal	$8.49 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ °C}^{-1}$	$2.32 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Pressure, p	17.5 Pa	Normal	$1.90 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$3.32 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w)$ / mol·mol⁻¹				$2.61 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Percent relative standard uncertainty, $100 \cdot u_c(x_w) / x_w$				0.54

Table 5: INRIM 03 uncertainty budget on the frost-point temperature, T_{fp} , pressure, p , and water vapour amount fraction, x_w at the following nominal values $T_{fp} = -95$ °C, $p = 1100$ hPa and $x_w = 35$ nmol·mol⁻¹.

$T_{fp} = -95$ °C $p = 1100$ hPa $x_w = 35$ nmol·mol⁻¹				
Uncertainty budget for T_{fp} / °C				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty / °C
Saturation temperature repeatability	0.0013 °C	Normal	1	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Saturator temperature uniformity	0.0016 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$
SPRT calibration	0.00025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Temperature resistance bridge accuracy	0.00043 °C	Rectangular	1	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT drift	0.0017 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Self-heating SPRT	0.00066 °C	Asym. Triangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Adsorption/Desorption	0.026 °C	Normal	1	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Saturation efficiency	0.012 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(T_{fp})$ / °C				0.029
Uncertainty budget for p / Pa				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ Pa
Pressure control stability	5.9 Pa	U-distribution	1	5.9
Transducer calibration	3.1 Pa	Normal	1	3.1
Long term stability	15.1 Pa	Rectangular	1	15.1
Linearity and temperature effects	7.6 Pa	Rectangular	1	7.6
Resolution	0.03 Pa	Rectangular	1	0.03
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(p)$ / Pa				18.2
Uncertainty budget for x_w / mol·mol⁻¹				

Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to Standard uncertainty/ mol·mol ⁻¹
Saturation pure water vapour pressure, $e(T_{fp})$	0.0000098 Pa	Normal	$9.18 \cdot 10^{-6}$ Pa ⁻¹	$8.96 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Enhancement factor, $f(T_{fp}, p)$	0.00067	Normal	$3.31 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$2.22 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Frost point temperature, T_{fp}	0.029 °C	Normal	$6.56 \cdot 10^{-9}$ °C ⁻¹	$1.88 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Pressure, p	18.2 Pa	Normal	$1.10 \cdot 10^{-14}$ Pa ⁻¹	$1.99 \cdot 10^{-13}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w)$ / mol·mol⁻¹				$2.10 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Percent relative standard uncertainty, $100 \cdot u_c(x_w) / x_w$				0.60

Table 6: INRIM 03 uncertainty budget on the frost-point temperature, T_{fp} , pressure, p , and water vapour amount fraction, x_w at the following nominal values $T_{fp} = -95$ °C, $p = 200$ hPa and $x_w = 189$ nmol·mol⁻¹.

$T_{fp} = -95$ °C $p = 200$ hPa $x_w = 189$ nmol·mol⁻¹				
Uncertainty budget for T_{fp} / °C				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ °C
Saturation temperature repeatability	0.00068 °C	Normal	1	$6.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Saturator temperature uniformity	0.00013 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT calibration	0.00025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Temperature resistance bridge accuracy	0.00043 °C	Rectangular	1	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT drift	0.0017 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Self-heating SPRT	0.00066 °C	Asym. Triangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Adsorption/Desorption	0.026 °C	Normal	1	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Saturation efficiency	0.0038	Rectangular	1	$3.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(T_{fp})$ / °C				0.026
Uncertainty budget for p / Pa				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ Pa
Pressure control stability	4.1 Pa	U-distribution	1	4.1
Transducer calibration	2.0 Pa	Normal	1	2.0
Long term stability	15.1 Pa	Rectangular	1	15.1
Linearity and temperature effects	7.6 Pa	Rectangular	1	7.6
Resolution	0.03 Pa	Rectangular	1	0.03
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(p)$ / Pa				17.5
Uncertainty budget for x_w / mol·mol⁻¹				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ mol·mol ⁻¹

Saturation pure water vapour pressure, $e(T_{fp})$	0.0000098 Pa	Normal	$5.01 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$4.87 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Enhancement factor, $f(T_{fp}, P)$	0.00012	Normal	$1.82 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$2.21 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Frost point temperature, T_{fp}	0.026 °C	Normal	$3.53 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ °C}^{-1}$	$9.23 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Pressure, p	17.5 Pa	Normal	$7.38 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w) / \text{mol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$				$1.05 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Percent relative standard uncertainty, $100 \cdot u_c(x_w) / x_w$				0.56

Table 7: INRIM 03 uncertainty budget on the frost-point temperature, T_{fp} , pressure, p , and water vapour amount fraction, x_w at the following nominal values: $T_{fp} = -100 \text{ °C}$, $p = 1100 \text{ hPa}$ and $x_w = 13 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$.

$T_{fp} = -100 \text{ °C}$ $p = 1100 \text{ hPa}$ $x_w = 13 \text{ nmol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$				
Uncertainty budget for $T_{fp} / \text{°C}$				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty / °C
Saturation temperature repeatability	0.0017 °C	Normal	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Saturator temperature uniformity	0.00049 °C	Rectangular	1	$4.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT calibration	0.00025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Temperature resistance bridge accuracy	0.00043 °C	Rectangular	1	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT drift	0.0017 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Self-heating SPRT	0.00066 °C	Asym. Triangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Adsorption/Desorption	0.025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Saturation efficiency	0.13 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-1}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(T_{fp}) / \text{°C}$				0.131
Uncertainty budget for p / Pa				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty / Pa
Pressure control stability	6.0 Pa	U-distribution	1	6.0
Transducer calibration	3.1 Pa	Normal	1	3.1
Long term stability	15.1 Pa	Rectangular	1	15.1
Linearity and temperature effects	7.6 Pa	Rectangular	1	7.6
Resolution	0.03 Pa	Rectangular	1	0.03
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(p) / \text{Pa}$				18.2
Uncertainty budget for $x_w / \text{mol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to Standard uncertainty / $\text{mol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
Saturation pure water vapour pressure, $e(T_{fp})$	0.0000048 Pa	Normal	$9.19 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$4.45 \cdot 10^{-11}$

Enhancement factor, $f(T_{fp}, p)$	0.00071	Normal	$1.55 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.10 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Frost point temperature, T_{fp}	0.131 °C	Normal	$3.20 \cdot 10^{-9}$ °C ⁻¹	$4.18 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Pressure, p	18.2 Pa	Normal	$1.14 \cdot 10^{-14}$ Pa ⁻¹	$2.08 \cdot 10^{-13}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w)$ / mol·mol⁻¹				$4.21 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Percent relative standard uncertainty, $100 \cdot u_c(x_w) / x_w$				3.24

Table 8: INRIM 03 uncertainty budget on the frost-point temperature, T_{fp} , pressure, p , and water vapour amount fraction, x_w at the following nominal values: $T_{fp} = -100$ °C, $p = 200$ hPa and $x_w = 70$ nmol·mol⁻¹.

$T_{fp} = -100$ °C $p = 200$ hPa $x_w = 70$ nmol·mol⁻¹				
Uncertainty budget for T_{fp} / °C				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ °C
Saturation temperature repeatability	0.0014 °C	Normal	1	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Saturator temperature uniformity	0.00024 °C	Rectangular	1	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT calibration	0.00025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Temperature resistance bridge accuracy	0.00043 °C	Rectangular	1	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$
SPRT drift	0.0017 °C	Rectangular	1	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Self-heating SPRT	0.00066 °C	Asym. Triangular	1	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$
Adsorption/Desorption	0.025 °C	Normal	1	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Saturation efficiency	0.0061	Rectangular	1	$6.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(T_{fp})$ / °C				0.026
Uncertainty budget for p / Pa				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ Pa
Pressure control stability	3.2 Pa	U-distribution	1	3.2
Transducer calibration	2.0 Pa	Normal	1	2.0
Long term stability	15.1 Pa	Rectangular	1	15.1
Linearity and temperature effects	7.6 Pa	Rectangular	1	7.6
Resolution	0.03 Pa	Rectangular	1	0.03
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(p)$ / Pa				17.3
Uncertainty budget for x_w / mol·mol⁻¹				
Source of uncertainty	Standard uncertainty	PDF	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution to combined uncertainty/ mol·mol ⁻¹
Saturation pure water vapour pressure, $e(T_{fp})$	0.0000048 Pa	Normal	$5.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Pa ⁻¹	$2.43 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Enhancement factor, $f(T_{fp}, P)$	0.00013	Normal	$8.51 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$1.10 \cdot 10^{-11}$

Frost point temperature, T_{fp}	0.026 °C	Normal	$1.72 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ °C}^{-1}$	$4.41 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Pressure, p	17.3 Pa	Normal	$3.42 \cdot 10^{-12} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$	$5.92 \cdot 10^{-11}$
Combined standard uncertainty, $u_c(x_w) / \text{mol} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$				$5.07 \cdot 10^{-10}$
Percent relative standard uncertainty, $100 \cdot u_c(x_w) / x_w$				0.72

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